

OVERCOMING GLOBAL PROBLEMS AND DEVELOPMENT STRATEGIES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10023987>

Abstract. *The article expresses an opinion about globalization processes in today's world, in particular, youth education and social protection of the needy in the family, neighborhood and educational institutions, strengthening the idea of patriotism through pedagogical education.*

Keywords: *patriotism, education and training, social and spiritual life, patriotism, social protection, military duty.*

Today, the processes of globalization are intensifying in the world, and new threats and dangers against peace and stability are increasing more and more. Such a complex and dangerous situation calls for a critical evaluation of the work done in the field and improvement of its activities based on the requirements of the times.

In particular, youth education in the family, neighborhood and educational institutions, purposeful ideological and educational work with unorganized youth in remote areas and neighborhoods is carried out in a superficial way, mistaken involvement in crime, religious extremism and terrorist activities, neglect of national values, early marriage, family separation, etc. the fact that promotional activities aimed at preventing negative situations do not give the expected results in most cases requires serious attention to these issues.

In the development strategy of the seven priority directions of the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026 adopted in our country, first of all, the priority task is to fundamentally improve the activities of the lower levels of state administration bodies, to ensure their communication with the people, and to strengthen the mechanism of effective social cooperation in this regard.

The reforms being carried out in Uzbekistan put before us the ideas that are humane and related to the destiny of the nation as an important task.

First, to realize that providing spiritual support to mothers and children is a huge phenomenon of the whole society and the whole country, and that each of us is responsible for it.

Second, to strengthen the sense of responsibility for social protection of mothers and children, to fully meet their daily needs.

Thirdly, the wide use of spiritual and educational opportunities, the use of literature that has a positive effect on the worldview and consciousness of our children, and their increase.

Fourth, active participation in solving problems related to mothers' and children's health.

Fifth, to create the necessary conditions for our children to quickly and deeply acquire modern knowledge, to widely use the most advanced experiences in the world education system.

Of course, solving these problems is not an easy task. However, it is necessary for us to be active in the implementation of state policies at a time when mothers and children are being

sponsored and cared for by the state itself. The Ministry of Public Education, Higher and Secondary Special Education, Health, Labor and Employment of the Republic of Uzbekistan, several state committees, the National Television and Radio Broadcasting Company, the Academy of Sciences should use all their capabilities to fully implement the current laws and government decisions.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis on December 22, 2017, he stated that the implementation of the adopted programs on the reform of the social sphere, which is an extremely important direction of the state policy in Uzbekistan, is being ensured step by step [1].

Public and non-governmental organizations, including "Mahalla" charitable public fund, "For a healthy generation" international fund, Women's Committee and other organizations should revive their activities in this area and increase their effectiveness.

On the basis of the above-mentioned opinions, it is the main requirement of today that the state and non-state organizations should focus their activities on the social system in a reciprocal manner regarding the problems of social protection. Since families are the main link of society, those in need of social protection can be conditionally divided into four categories:

- the poor,
- the needy,
- the poor,
- low-income families.

In our country, social protection of the population is aimed at providing material support to active families, especially families with many children, and this process is aimed at providing financial support to extremely needy and needy families.

According to UN expert Keith Griffin, "This system is based on a long (traditional, historical) development that is thorough and inexpensive, and has won the trust of the local population" [2].

However, the effective use of allocated funds increases the responsibility of local government bodies.

The new family institution of social assistance, leaving out a large number of leaders, on the basis of its decision, paves the way to a certain extent to distribute a part of the gross domestic product in favor of the really needy parts of the population.

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 27, 2018 on approving the concept of strengthening the family institution in the Republic of Uzbekistan, one of the important factors of the targeted reforms being carried out in our country is to strengthen the moral support of young families, to instill in young people a sense of pride and responsibility for the new family they have built, to parents, We will strengthen the foundation of our future by forming feelings of respect for the representatives of the older generation, hard work and the desire to raise children in the spirit of the eternal spiritual values of our people.

One of the most important and sacred human rights in any free and prosperous country is the right to live in peace and tranquility. The main duty of the state and society is to guarantee this right by all legal means. Implementation of this right is the most important condition for democratization of the state and society.

Along with the changes in our lives and our achievements, there are also big problems that need to be solved. During the short period that has passed since the declaration of independence,

there have been great social, political, economic and spiritual changes in the history of our nation and state. Considerable steps have been taken in the restoration of our national statehood, centuries-old incomparable spiritual heritage, history, culture, religion, language, and sacred traditions. Our national pride and honor are being restored, true patriotism is awakening in our hearts. Uzbekistan is building its own life by choosing a unique and suitable path of development.

Today's main task is to accelerate the implementation of economic reforms to raise the standard of living of the people. These are:

- filling our domestic market with both cheap and quality consumer goods;
- implementation of financial, bank-credit policy to sharply reduce state expenses;
- increasing the weight of competitive products and sharply strengthening export opportunities;
- opening a guaranteed wide path for entrepreneurship, small and medium-sized business;
- complete computerization of the field of education;
- increase the capacity of pedagogic personnel;
- liberalization of agricultural sectors, that is, step-by-step industrialization of the agrarian sector, is one of the important conditions of our time. At the same time, the extent to which the reforms are carried out depends on the outlook of the leaders, being honest and clean, entrepreneurial and proactive.

Another important principle of the reforms is the protection and social protection of the underprivileged population, that is, the elderly, disabled, orphans and children. It is not without reason that the population relies on the system of self-management in the implementation of these goals, namely, the neighborhoods that are of great importance in our lives. The scope of work planned by the government requires the need to solve labor market problems, attract labor force, and create additional jobs in rural areas.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev in his speech at the extended video selector meeting on April 11, 2018 - "We all solve the life problems that concern our compatriots in a timely manner through consistent and proportionate development of our country and its territories in terms of socio-economic and constant and open communication with our people. and we should always bear in mind that we have taken on the large-scale tasks of creating decent living conditions for the population in an effective way, and we should actively work on this basis" [3].

At a time when all aspects of the country's social life, including the processes of liberalization of state and community life, are deepening and gaining new meaning and meaning, it is of great importance to increase the influence of non-governmental structures and public organizations. Because it is possible to increase the socio-economic, political-cultural activity of citizens and the full potential of a person through these non-governmental organizations. Through this system, people have the right to realize their interests, openly expressing their aspirations. However, special emphasis should be placed on the incomparable role of the state in the implementation of social protection. Because only the state makes important decisions regarding the strongest social policy in carrying out such work.

The state budget, extra-budgetary non-governmental non-profit organizations, public associations, various charity funds, funds of enterprises and farms, as well as voluntary donations of citizens, etc., are the source of material assistance in alleviating the problems of social protection. In reality, the people should not serve the state agencies, but the state agencies should

serve our people on the basis of ensuring legislation, achieving justice in the judicial and legal system, ensuring citizens' confidence in the future, and raising the human factor by giving an impartial assessment of the activities of internal affairs and the prosecutor's office, which are considered state bodies. shows the necessity. The vitality of the developed laws and their implementation should be given priority in the society. Now, in the state and non-state sector and in the entire production, not ordinary working hands are needed, but specialist employees, employees who are quickly involved in economic reforms, experts who meet the requirements of market relations and the requirements of modern world technology. Therefore, it is an important task to eliminate the gap between the growth rate of the labor force, the transition from general production to advanced technology, the increase in the volume of export of products, and the training of employees with a new mindset in today's market conditions.

The essence of the large-scale reforms implemented under the leadership of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev calls people to understand and feel the human factor in life and internal possibilities more deeply, and not to shy away from work. The spiritual and physical maturity of the citizens, especially the youth of the country, combined with feeling, understanding, learning and understanding of high civic responsibility through the idea of national development, peace and well-being of the country, as well as a sense of commitment to the society, will be a solid foundation for the realization of our great goals.

Resolution PQ-3898 of August 4, 2018 of the Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the fundamental improvement of the system of raising the morale-educational level of the military personnel of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and morale-educational work in the Armed Forces system introduced on this basis in accordance with the concept of increasing the effectiveness of "Holy Motherland, it is an honorable duty to protect it!" idea was put forward. Also, in the Armed Forces system, every Friday of the week is designated as the "Day of Moral Elevation and Patriotism", and it is necessary to encourage the moral and spiritual training of military personnel. The goal is to protect the sovereignty of our country, territorial integrity, and the peace of our people with loyalty, which is recognized as the highest task. Wide-scale reforms are being implemented in our country to strengthen peace and stability, ensure human rights, freedoms and interests, comprehensively develop our country, and raise its prestige in the international arena.

In fact, during the past 32 years of independence, Uzbekistan has strengthened its position in the world axis by relying on our great values with its democratic reforms. In a short period of time, in the development of New Uzbekistan, extensive reforms in all areas will further strengthen the power of our country.

Therefore, based on the meaning of the Development Strategy on the seven priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022-2026 and the State Program "Year of attention to people and quality education", the main ideas and principles of this decision show that the human factor is in the first place as a guarantee of our peace.

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